

CLINICAL EXPERT GROUP

MEMBERSHIP

Membership includes clinical experts on children and adolescents in relation to gender, development, physical and mental health, neurodiversity, safeguarding and endocrinology.

	TITLE	ORGANISATION	S40
Dr Hilary Cass	Chair	Independent review of gender identity services for children and young people	S40
S40	S40 Consultant, Child and Adolescent Psychiatry	NHS England	S40
S40	S40 Professor of Nursing	Multi-Professional Review group	S40
S40	S40 Consultant Paediatrician	Paediatric Mental Health Association	S40
S40	Child and Adolescent Psychotherapist	Association of Child Psychotherapists (Child & Adolescent Psychotherapist)	S40
S40	S40 General Paediatrics and Adolescent Medicine	Young People's Health Special Interest Group	S40
S40	S40 Consultant Clinical Psychologist	Gender Identity Development Service, Tavistock and Portman NHS Foundation Trust	S40
S40	Clinical Psychologist and gender specialist	Gender Identity Development Service, Tavistock and Portman NHS Foundation Trust	S40
S40	Clinical Nurse Specialist	University College London Hospitals	S40
S40	Consultant Community Paediatrician S40	Evelina London, Guy's and St Thomas'	S40

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S40	Consultant Child and Adolescent Psychiatrist	Royal Manchester Children's Hospital	S40
S40	Consultant Clinical Psychologist S40	South London and Maudsley NHS Foundation Trust	S40
S40	Consultant Child and Adolescent Psychiatrist S40	South London and Maudsley NHS Foundation Trust	S40
S40	S40 Clinical Psychologist and Neuropsychologist	Association of Clinical Psychologists	S40
S40	General Paediatric Consultant	Great Ormond Street Hospital	S40
S40	S40 CAMHS	Alder Hey Children's Hospital	S40
S40	Consultant Clinical Psychologist S40	University Hospital Bristol NHS Trust	S40
S40	S40 Consultant Psychiatrist S40	Royal College of Psychiatrists	S40
S40	GP S40	RCGP/Primary Care	S40

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S40	GP S40	RCGP	S40
S40	Consultant Paediatrician S40	Sandwell and West Birmingham Hospitals NHS Trust	S40
S40	S40 Children & Young People's Mental Health	NHS England, Specialised commissioning	S40
S40	Designated Doctor for Safeguarding and Looked After Children S40	NNDHP	S40
S40	Clinical Psychologist S40	Co-opt for assessment piece	S40

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S40	S40 Consultant Clinical Psychologist	SLAM	S40
S40	S40 Adult Gender Consultant	Co-opt	S40
	Education – seeking representation		